

Finland

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Finland, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report¹ on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

The Finnish higher education system comprises 13 universities and 22 universities of applied sciences in the Ministry of Education and Culture sector. Higher education institutions are mainly multi-field institutions.

University-level education is also provided by a military institution of higher education, the National Defence University, which is part of the Defence Forces. At university of applied sciences -level there is the Åland University of Applied Sciences in the self-governing Province of Åland and the Police University College of Finland subordinate to the Ministry of the Interior.

Both types of HE institutions have their own purposes according to legislation.

The purpose of **Universities** is to:

- promote independent academic research and academic and artistic education.
- provide higher education based on research.

The purpose of **Universities of Applied Sciences** is to:

- provide higher education for professional expert jobs based on the requirements of working life.
- carry out applied research, development and innovation activities and artistic activities that promote industry, business and regional development and regenerate the industrial structure of the region.

Universities provide Bachelor's, Master's and third-cycle postgraduate degrees. Students at universities of applied sciences can complete Bachelor's and Master's degrees. In addition, universities and universities of applied sciences can provide professional specialisation programmes and non-degree study modules.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Universities (*Yliopisto*) are all public institutions and have the right to award PhDs. In total, about 37% of all Finnish HEIs are Universities and equivalent institutions. Universities of Applied Sciences (*Ammattikorkeakoulu*) account for almost 63% of all Finnish HEIs, however, none of them awards PhDs; the majority (22) of Universities of Applied Sciences are private, while only a few (2) are public.

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/finland/types-higher-education-institutions>

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private government-dependent	PhD awarding
University	Yliopisto	14	14	0	14
University of Applied Sciences	Ammattikorkeakoulu	24	2	22	0
Total		38	16	22	14

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Finland's higher education and its evolution over time. Figure 1 shows that the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent, for Universities (*Yliopisto*) quite steadily after 1960, while for Universities of Applied Sciences (*Ammattikorkeakoulut*) after 1990, with an enormous increase between 1990 and 2000. The University of Helsinki is the oldest Finnish university, dating back to 1640; since then, only three further Universities have been established before the 1960s (Hanken School of Economics in 1909, Abo Akademi University in 1918 and University of Turku in 1920).

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of students across the two HEI categories of the Finish HE system. It can be seen that Universities - while accounting just for around one third in terms of the number of institutions – enroll almost half of the total students at Bachelor and Master levels (48%), and naturally all PhD students (given that universities of applied sciences are all non PhD awarding). Looking at Master students enrolment (excluding Master long degrees), Universities account for almost 80%, while for Bachelor students, around 60% are enrolled in Universities of Applied Sciences. Master students long degree are exclusively subject to Universities.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown by Figure 3, there are major differences between HEIs in size, as measured by total personnel in full time equivalents (FTE), and in the personnel composition. While there is a larger number of universities of applied sciences (24), the majority of personnel is affiliated with the 14 universities in Finland, i.e. they are much larger in terms of personnel accounting for around 75% of total staff across different staff categories. Regarding the personnel composition, the share does not differ much between universities and universities of applied sciences and is around 65% for academic staff, and around 10% for research and teaching assistants. However, the share of support and administrative personnel is somewhat higher for universities (27%) than for universities of applied sciences (23%).

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT². Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

For Finland, we find a very strong intermediate component in the staff composition pointing to a more flat hierarchy, with nearly 35% of academic personnel being at intermediate level. This is surrounded by a 20% share of juniors and a 10% share of seniors, respectively. A remarkably high share (24%) cannot be classified by seniority level which is an issue for improvement in future data collection.

² OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

Note: Unclassified personnel is not included in figure

A final important dimension is internationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research and education. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown by Figure 5, Finland's higher education is characterized by a rather medium to low level of internationality with about 25% of foreign academic personnel in universities. However, the degree of internationalization has increased between 2014 and 2020 from below 20% foreign staff. University of applied sciences have a very small degree of internationalization, but it has about doubled between 2014 and 2020.

Figure 5. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2014 and 2020

Financial resources

As illustrated by **Error! Reference source not found.6**, in the year 2020, Universities account for more than 70% of financial revenues and academic personnel of the whole HEI system, i.e., substantially more than their share of total students. This broadly corresponds to the fact that Universities also have an important research function. This difference is also reflected in the composition of revenues (Figure 7), where Universities receive a large proportion of revenues from the core budget and (research-related) third-party funds. Overall, state allocation remains dominant for all institutional types in Finland; student fees are not at stake.

Figure 6. Resources, academic personnel and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Figure 7. Composition of resources. Universities (Yliopisto) and Universities of Applied Sciences (Ammattikorkeakoulu)

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a rather stable pattern over the observed time period, with just a slight decrease of total students from 2011 until 2017, and a stabilization and

minor increase after 2017. The distribution between Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences is also just subject to very minor changes, in particular after 2015 (from 2011 to 2015 the share of universities slightly decreased).

Figure 8. Share of students enrolled type of HEI, 2011-2020

As shown by Figure 9, the number of academic personnel (FTE) in Finland is nearly proportional to the number of students. Even the slight decrease in the number of students between 2014 and 2017 is also observable for the academic personnel, even a bit more pronounced than for students. However, the size of academic personnel is overall stable over the observed time period and in 2020 nearly at the same level as in 2011.

Figure 9. Academic personnel (FTE) type of HEI, 2011-2020

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